

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF ANTHRANILIC ACID COMPLEXES

Molar ratio Metal : ligand	Complexes	% found			% Calculated		
		Metal	C	N	Metal	C	N
1 : 1	[Zr A (OH) ₂](OH)	32.91	31.61	5.05	32.73	30.22	5.04
1 : 2	[Th(A) ₂ (OH) ₂]	46.05	33.34	5.45	43.12	31.23	5.23
1 : 4	[Th(A) ₃](OH)	36.31	39.38	6.25	35.31	37.97	6.35

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT BANDS IN THE SPECTRA OF HA AND ITS COMPLEXES

Compound	ν (NH) ν (OH) (Cm ⁻¹)	&	ν (OH) bonded (Cm ⁻¹)	ν (CO) (Cm ⁻¹)	Ring vibration (Cm ⁻¹)	Antisymmetric carboxylate ion vibration (Cm ⁻¹)
HA	3480m		2598m	16770s	1615 s, 1580 s, 1521 s, 1610 s, 1570 s, 1505 m	1398 s
[Zr(A) (OH) ₂](OH)	3450m 3330m		—	—	1605 m, 1560 m, 1495 sh	1420 s
[Tr(A) ₂ (OH)] ₂	3418s, 3315s		—	—	1605 s, 1575 s, 1505 s	1425 s
[Th(A) ₃](OH)	3420m, 3320m		—	—		1430 s

The conductometric and potentiometric titrations at 27°C were carried out by the same methods and experimental set up as reported earlier¹. The complexes were isolated and their infrared spectra were examined with films on KBr plates in the range of 400-4000 cm⁻¹ by perkin-Elmer I. R. 337 grating spectrophotometer and representative assignments of HA and its complexes are given in Table II.

Zirconyl ion seems to form the complexes of the general formula [Zr (OH)₂ (L)] OH, where HL is the ligand. Thorium forms 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complexes with all the acids, which was confirmed by direct conductivity and potentiometric titrations. The complex with molar ratio 1:1 could not be isolated, whereas, the complex with stoichiometric ratios 1:2 and 1:3 were isolated.

Infrared Spectra :

The bands occurring in the spectra of ligands and complexes in 3480-3355 cm⁻¹ region² are due to NH and OH stretching frequency. The negative shifts of 60 cm⁻¹ to cm⁻¹ in both NH stretching bands, suggest that amino group is involved in co-ordination.

The bands due to the hydroxyl group of COOH and the carbonyl group are absent in the complexes. Thus it appears that HA and its halo derivatives act as bidentate ligands, which is also supported by the work of Decker et. al. 3,4.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. Ram Gopal, Head of the Chemistry Deptt. for providing laboratory facilities and C.S.I.R. for awarding a fellowship to one of us (G.N.M.).

References

1. C. S. PANDE and G. N. MISRA., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 292.
2. R. C. AGARWAL and R. P. SINGH., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 2593.
3. J. S. DECKER and H. FRYE., *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1966, **B 21**, 522.
4. J. S. DECKER and H. FRYE., *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1966, **B 21**, 527.

Amperometric Titration of Lead with Phosphorus Pentasulphide & its Determination in Presence of Mercury and Silver

H. CHAUDHURI, S. S. CHATTERJEE & H. S. MAHANTI
Chemistry Department, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-5.

Manuscript received 4 June 1973, revised 8 July 1974,
accepted 23 July 1974.

ALTHOUGH few references are available for amperometric determination of lead,¹⁻⁵ there is no published data regarding the amperometric estimation of lead in presence of mercury and silver. In the present investigation, phosphorus pentasulphide has been used as an analytical reagent for the amperometric estimation of lead, which has also been determined in presence of mercury and silver. For the determination of lead, the method is based on the measurement of anodic current of the excess titrating agent after the end-point. For the estimation of the constituents of binary solutions, the method is based on the decrease in height of the reduction wave of the uncombined metal ion and increase in anodic current of excess titrant.

*Present address : National Institute of Foundry & Forge Technology, Hatia, Ranchi-3.

Solutions of lead, mercury and silver were obtained from E. Merck's samples and standardized by gravimetric methods⁶. All other reagents used were of AnalaR varieties. Phosphorus pentasulphide solution was prepared by dissolving weighed quantity of the reagent in dil. NH_4OH and standardized either with sodium hypobromite amperometrically at an applied potential $+0.1\text{V}$ (vs SCE) using rotating platinum micro-electrode or with sodium hypiodite volumetrically in an alkaline medium. Ammoniacal solution of the reagent is stable for 24 hr. The reagent should be freshly prepared daily and standardized before use.

Titration curves were carried out in Fisher Electrode in conjunction with SCE and dropping mercury electrode. pH measurements were made with a line operated Beckman Zeromatic pH meter.

Procedure—Preliminary observations showed that lead, mercury and silver can be estimated quantitatively in a medium consisting of ammonium tartrate and potassium nitrate (overall concentration 0.05-0.25M) within the pH range of 7.5 to 9.5. In the actual procedure, an aliquot of lead solution was taken in a pyrex beaker containing 20 ml of 0.1M buffer and pH of the solution was adjusted to 8.5 by adding aq. ammonia. A potential of -0.2V (vs SCE) was applied and galvanometer reading was noted initially and after each addition of the titrant. After complete precipitation of lead, excess reagent gave the anodic diffusion current of its own resulting in a regular rise in the current. The plot of the volume of the reagent galvanometer reading is shown in Fig. 1 (Curve A).

Fig. 1 : Typical Amperometric Titration Curves

Estimation of lead and mercury in a binary mixture :

The titrations were carried out at an applied potential of -0.2V (vs SCE). An aliquot of a solution containing lead and mercury was taken in a pyrex beaker containing the above buffer (0.1M) and the pH of the medium

was adjusted to 8.0 with ammonia. The diffusion current was noted initially. As the addition of the reagent continued, the diffusion current of mercury reduced gradually and became steady. This intersection (Fig. 1, curve B) gave the end-point for mercury. With further addition of the titrant lead started getting precipitated and when whole of lead was removed excess of the reagent gave the anodic diffusion current of its own. The intersection at this point gave the end-point for lead.

Estimation of lead and silver : The procedure adopted in this determination was identical to that mentioned above.

Results obtained under these conditions showed that 0.4 to 5.0 mg of lead, mercury and silver can be determined accurately. It may be pointed out that the procedure is simple and easily adoptable.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to Prof. G. S. Deshmukh for helpful discussions and to the C.S.I.R., for the award of a fellowship to one of them (H.S.M.).

References

1. V. MAJER., *Z. Electrochem.*, 1936, 42, 120.
2. I. M. KOLTHOFF and Y. D. PAN., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 3402.
3. S. L. GUPTA and S. K. SHARMA., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 381.
4. W. STRICKS and S. K. CHAKRABORTY., *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, 34, 508.
5. G. S. DESHMUKH and V. S. S. RAO., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 37.
6. A. I. VOGEL., "A textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis" Longmans, Green & Co., London, 1961, p. 482 and 486.

Estimation of Fly Ash Content in Portland Fly Ash Cement

S. S. REHSI and S. K. GARG

Central Building Research Institute, Roorkee

Manuscript received 24 July 1974 ; accepted 26 July 1974

THE presence of fly ash in cement can be detected by (i) change in colour when a sample of the cement is heated at 800° or higher and (ii) floating of fly ash particles at the surface when a small quantity of the cement is shaken in water and kept undisturbed for a few minutes. While these tests can be usefully employed for checking adulteration of normal portland cement with fly ash, their application to known portland fly ash cement (pfc) is pointless. In pfc a quantitative estimation of fly ash content is needed. A method involving extraction of pozzolana cement with a solution of picric acid in methyl alcohol leaving a residue of